

IMPROVEMENT OF DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC LARYNGITIS

Samieva Gulnoza Utkurovna

DSc., Professor,

Head of the Department of Pathological Physiology

Sabirova Shakhlo Bakhtiyorovna

Assistant,

Department of Folk and Sports Medicine

Tolibdjanov Bobur Talatovich

Medical Student

Samarkand State Medical University

Samarkand, Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18516957>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 05th February 2026

Accepted: 06th February 2026

Online: 07th February 2026

KEYWORDS

To evaluate the effectiveness of an improved diagnostic algorithm and comprehensive treatment of patients with chronic laryngitis based on clinical, instrumental, and functional research methods

ABSTRACT

Chronic laryngitis represents one of the most significant problems in modern otorhinolaryngology due to its high prevalence, tendency to recurrent course, and pronounced negative impact on vocal function and patients' social activity. Conventional diagnostic and therapeutic approaches do not always ensure stable clinical remission, which determines the need for the implementation of comprehensive and personalized diagnostic and treatment strategies.

Chronic laryngitis represents one of the most significant problems in modern otorhinolaryngology due to its high prevalence, tendency to recurrent course, and pronounced negative impact on vocal function and patients' social activity. Conventional diagnostic and therapeutic approaches do not always ensure stable clinical remission, which determines the need for the implementation of comprehensive and personalized diagnostic and treatment strategies.

Objective.

To evaluate the effectiveness of an improved diagnostic algorithm and comprehensive treatment of patients with chronic laryngitis based on clinical, instrumental, and functional research methods.

Materials and Methods.

The study included 68 patients with various clinical forms of chronic laryngitis (catarrhal, hypertrophic, and atrophic forms) aged 25 to 60 years. The control group consisted of 30 patients who received standard therapy. All patients underwent a comprehensive clinical examination including videolaryngoscopy, videostroboscopy, acoustic voice analysis (Jitter, Shimmer, and HNR parameters), and assessment of vocal function using the Voice Handicap Index (VHI). In the main group, an improved therapeutic algorithm was applied, comprising anti-inflammatory therapy, inhalation treatment, local physiotherapy, voice therapy, and individualized vocal load management.

Results and Discussion.

After completion of the treatment course, the main group demonstrated a statistically significant improvement in clinical and functional parameters. According to videostroboscopic findings, restoration of symmetrical vibration of the vocal folds and a reduction in signs of chronic inflammation were observed in 82.4% of patients, whereas this indicator reached only 56.7% in the control group. Acoustic analysis revealed a significant decrease in Jitter and Shimmer values and an increase in the harmonic-to-noise ratio (HNR). The mean VHI score decreased from 48.6 ± 3.2 to 21.4 ± 2.8 points, indicating a substantial improvement in patients' quality of life.

Conclusion.

The use of a comprehensive diagnostic approach and an improved treatment algorithm for chronic laryngitis provides a more pronounced clinical and functional effect compared to standard therapy. The obtained results confirm the feasibility of implementing personalized diagnostic and therapeutic programs in routine otorhinolaryngological practice..

References:

1. Bastian R. W. Videostroboscopy in the evaluation of voice disorders // *Laryngoscope*. — 2019. — Vol. 129, № 3. — P. 623–629.
2. Cohen S. M., Garrett C. G. Effectiveness of voice therapy in chronic inflammatory laryngeal disease // *Annals of Otology, Rhinology & Laryngology*. — 2020. — Vol. 129, № 5. — P. 456–462.
3. Rosen C. A., Murry T. Voice disorders and voice therapy outcomes // *Otolaryngology–Head and Neck Surgery*. — 2019. — Vol. 161, № 2. — P. 234–240.
4. Sataloff R. T. *Professional voice: the science and art of clinical care*. — 4th ed. — New York : Thieme Medical Publishers, 2020. — 1328 p.
5. Woo P. Chronic laryngitis: diagnosis and management // *Otolaryngologic Clinics of North America*. — 2018. — Vol. 51, № 4. — P. 701–715